

Impact of Artificial Light at Night (ALAN) on Collective Grooming Behaviour in a Freshwater Prawn Population (*Macrobrachium Lamarrei*)

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Abstract: Anthropogenic activities and their adverse effects have been acknowledged as one of the most critical areas of research, particularly for behavioural ecologists. Artificial Light at Night (ALAN) is one such anthropogenic hazard that has immense pervasive repercussions yet is often disregarded. Despite being perceived merely as a passive pollutant, ALAN actively disrupts critical ecological and physiological processes, including robust behavioural patterns crucial for species survival. Our experimentations aimed to assess the ALAN altered collective grooming (population-based) patterns, over time in a freshwater prawn species, *Macrobrachium lamarrei*. In order to determine the effects of ALAN on the neuro-circadian cascade of these organisms we tried to focus on the collective grooming behaviour plasticity in these organisms. The findings elucidated that ALAN insult can induce notable upliftment in the collective grooming activity after 4th day of prolonged light exposure, in comparison to the normal light-dark cycle, indicating an elevated grooming plasticity. Results indicated a tendency of significantly exponential increase of grooming activity from 4th day onwards. Through this work, we want to understand the behavioural plasticity and adaptive modifications in response to extended ALAN exposure, as well as forecast how ALAN plays a major role in triggering artificial light sensitivity and regulating brain functions in animals. We want to demonstrate how prolonged artificial light exposure can affect the brain behaviour circuit of *Macrobrachium lamarrei*.

Keywords: artificial light at night (ALAN), collective grooming, prawns, neurobehavioural stress.

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